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EMPLOYEE SATISFACTION WHILE KEEPING UP WITH EMPLOYEE LEGISLATION

* Dr. Krishna Kishore,

** Prof. Manjula Rani ,

*&**Asst. Professor, Alliance University, Bangalore, India.

Abstract

In the recent times, many amendments have been made to the existing labour laws in India. The government of India has made many amendments to ensure the well being of the labourers as well the employees. These laws also seek to simplify the process of dealing with the trade unions as well as the wageworkers. Change is a needed attribute in the world. Judging by this, the government has also introduced many new laws for the benefit of the employees.

Human resources being a vital factor for running a business undergo the process of recruiting and training employees, identifying and meeting the needs of the employee staff and ensuring employee welfare are some of the major functions performed by the Human Resource department. However, this department would remain highly inefficient and redundant if it does not adhere to the rules and regulations as cited by the government of India. Hence, it is imperative for any organization to keep themselves up-to-date with the various changes that occur in the labour laws and keeping up to date employee legislation.

This research aims to highlight the need for continuous revision of HR policies to keep pace with the various changes in the labour laws and present an overview of various important amendments of laws passed and the

necessary steps that need to be taken by the human resource departments of an organization, to avoid any chaos or dissatisfaction on the part of the employees. Some of the acts are taken for the purpose of research as verbatim from the official websites and referred as required, so that the meaning may not change.

The research also aims to account the changes in the legislation of industrial relations and establish the growing need of human resources rather than industrial relations. This research concludes by highlighting the importance of constant modifications of the policies of the various firms to incorporate all these labour laws into being.

Key Word: *Employee Legislation, Labour Laws, HR professionals, Amendments, Employee Satisfaction.*

[^]Corresponding author: * Dr. Krishna Kishore

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Introduction:

Employee Legislation is one of the core functions of the Human Resource Department in any organization. The entire employee life cycle in any organization, right from Selection process to exit including training, compensation, reward administration and disciplining staff, a special attention must be paid to the relevant labour regulations. Failure to abide by these laws can lead to resentful employees, government fines and lawsuits. The relations between labour and management remain healthy only if organization adheres to the uniform policies and laws. The knowledge of employment laws for HR professionals will always be the advantage to manage employees effectively. Keeping up with the labor laws can mitigate any kind of legal and ethical risk to which the organization may be exposed.

Employee legislation addresses the legal rights of the employers as well as the employees in various acts. The concept of human resources however started with industrial relations concept, post industrial revolution there were quite a lot of amendments in the legislations. Post LPG few more amendments has taken place in the acts and are being reworked and amended on a regular basis for benefit of employee and also the employers. The amendments have taken place from setting uniform and transparent selection process, setting legal compliances, employee rights, minimum compensation payouts, benefits administration, and many more legislative changes are undergoing fabrications.

Everything from working hours, holiday entitlement and well being and safety in the workplace to equality and diversity are all problems covered by employment law and hence, it is essential for both employers and well as employees to be well versed with their respective rights. Issues such as minimum wage, employment contracts as well as business transfers are all very crucial pieces of legislation for any organization.

In addition to employment acts, approved code of conduct, such as time of work for trade union duties also impact the decisions of employees. So, realizing what can be provided to the employee and the legal obligations is absolutely essential if organization is aiming to achieve a secure and harmonious working environment. Most responsible employers keep up to date with employment law and comprehend its significance, and those who do not end up being prosecuted.

The penalties for not adhering to relevant legislation vary according to the offence. If you are an employer the finest way to make sure

that you stay on the proper side of the law is to be up to date with the newest employment legislation.

Employers and employees may not be updated of the recent changes that may have occurred in the labour laws. Running a business and keeping up with the prospective changes in the laws may be cumbersome but it is essential that all the employers do so. Employee satisfaction is directly correlated to the legislations and employers commitment to get the amendments into practice without delaying the process.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizations often make mistakes; sometimes they land up paying very high penalties for a small mistake. This happens quite often because of disconnection of HR function with the management or no HR department or not taking any advices from HR consultants. These mistakes can be evaded with a professional HR advice from an internal HR professional or an external HR consultant. Not only legal issues, but also fairly common employment-related mistakes result in costs to the organization in terms of lost productivity, efficiency, effectiveness, sales and revenues, and decreased profitability, Mathews (2006).

Employment laws are often difficult to understand or interpret. They can vary from state to state, an amendments happens on a regular basis. Even the best-trained HR professionals are challenged to keep up with changes in employment law.

Employers may be classified into various types. The three major classifications of misinterpretation are fraudulent, negligent and innocent. This not only includes the traditional cause of action of deceit, but also the emerging tort of negligent misinterpretations in the employment context.

The increased incidence of disciplinary damages awards is due to judicial expansion of the circumstances under which disciplinary damages are available. One context in which the application of a corrective remedy is particularly controversial is the new and rapidly expanding are of law granting rights of action for the wrongful discharge of employee whose job security is not guaranteed by express contract, collective bargaining agreement, statutory provision or tenure system, Mallor (1999)

Rosenberg (2000), opines that routine personnel matters have high potential to become serious cause for personal injury litigation with disastrous financial consequences for an

organization and its owners. Indeed, hardly a week goes by without a report of a substantial settlement or jury award involving claims of workplace discrimination, sex harassment or wrongful termination. Law firms certainly have had their share of these cases. How is it that an organization's greatest asset which is its employees, is also the source of its greatest exposure and what can be done to minimize this risk? At the root of the problem is the failure to appreciate that the employment relationship is one of the most regulated business relationships of all. Also, firms today operate in an increasingly litigious environment. Employees are a lot more exposed on the laws matters and they are easily accessible on the mobile phones also (Rosenberg, 2000). The recent right to information act also states about no employee can be denied for any information they needed.

Keeping up with all of the changes and amendments in employment law should be a full-time job and there should be a dedicated employee for doing the same. Many organizations treat this important task as a clerical job, and it will be assigned to office manager/executives or whoever supervises the organizations personnel matters. As many organizations have found out the hard way, allowing under-trained people to preside over personnel transactions is asking for trouble. (Rosenberg, 2000)

One of the major employment litigation against organizations is that the employee proclaims that the firm failed to live up to a promise made at the time of hire (or later) on about job assignments, career progression and the similar. This is especially prevalent with lateral hires, or contract employees and those who come into the organizations with non-traditional arrangements. One noticeable approach to protect organizations against such allegations is to put all significant employment arrangements in writing. Legal documentation plays a major role to solve this kind of problems. Documentary evidences are always life savers for the organizations. A written employment agreement specifying how and when the employment relationship started, and how it can be ended, and the financial consequences of doing so, has to be included in such documents. (Collins, 2009).

For an instance, under no circumstance can an organization's at-will policy save a termination, which violates the law. Nor can an organization rely solely on the at-will rule to terminate an employee out on extended medical leave or the employee who reveals that she is pregnant and will need several months maternity leave. It is risky for the firm to rely solely on its people

managers' intuition when carrying out personnel transactions because so many of the employment laws are counter intuitive. (ctopengovt.org, 2014)

Many observers have argued that India's labour laws should be reformed. The laws have constrained the growth of the formal manufacturing sector. According to a World Bank report in 2008, heavy reforms and amendments are desirable in various acts. The Indian labor regulations act, which is among the most restrictive and complex in the world - have constrained the growth of the formal manufacturing sector where these laws have their widest application. Better-designed labor regulations can attract more labor-intensive investment and create jobs for India's unemployed millions and those trapped in poor quality of jobs, work culture and hostile environment. The country's momentum of growth and the window of opportunity must not be lost for improving the job prospects for the 80 million new entrants who are expected to join the work force over the next decade. (World Bank Report, 2008)

Scholars suggest India's rigid labor laws bureaucratic acts and laws along with excessive regulations assumed to protect the labour are the cause of slow employment growth and low paying in an organized as well as unorganized sector. This approach is slowing down the productivity and lower employee satisfaction and morale. India's labour-related acts and regulations have led to labour market rigidity. This encourages shadow economy for entrepreneurs, an economy that prefers to employ informal labour to avoid the complicated and opaque laws.

In particular, Indian labor legislation such as the Industrial Disputes Act of 1947 added rigid labour laws and one-sided trade union laws. Although the Act does not prohibit layoffs and retrenchments, it does require entrepreneurs and companies to get the permission from government officials to fire an employee for absenteeism, retrench employees for economic reasons, or to close an economically nonviable company. This bureaucratic process can stretch into years, and the government officials have consistently and almost always denied such permission. Excessive rigidity in labour laws can lead to de-motivation of employees and lead to excessive attrition (recruitor.com). This can be one major reason why most of the small and medium scale industries do not flourish in India, in spite of having highest potential in itself.

FEW AMENDED ACTS AND ITS IMPACT ON EMPLOYEES

Indian government is taking necessary steps to amend the acts for greater public benefit. This is quite encouraging for many employees across the various sectors and creating confidence in working for SME's along with IT sector. For an instance to discuss, The Union Cabinet approved the introduction of the Women Protection against Sexual Harassment at Workplace Bill, 2010 in the Parliament to ensure a safe working environment for women at work places, both in public and private sectors whether organized or unorganized. The measure will help in achieving gender empowerment. The proposed Bill, if enacted, will ensure that women are protected against sexual harassment at all the work places, be it in public or private. This will contribute to realization of their right to gender equality, life and liberty and equality in working conditions everywhere. The sense of security at the workplace will improve women's participation in work, resulting in their economic empowerment and inclusive growth. The addition of this act brought a markeable confidence in women employees and as well as their families. The confidence of personal and professional security allows employees to concentrate on the work which will turn into higher productivity by itself. The sense of security at the workplace will improve women's participation in work, resulting in their economic empowerment and inclusive growth (GOI, 2010). The higher the satisfaction the higher the productivity. The amendments of the acts also develop the quality of work life.

The Parliament also passed the Employees' State Insurance (Amendment) Bill, 2009. The Employees' State Insurance Scheme is a welfare scheme framed for workers covered under the Employees' State Insurance Act, 1948 providing for medical benefits for the employees and their families and payment of benefits to the employees in cases of sickness, maternity and employment injury. The Scheme is applicable to power-using factories employing 10 or more persons and non-power using factories and certain other establishments employing 20 or more persons. Keeping in-view the changing economic scenario, the Act needed important amendments. These amendments will ensure coverage of more workers under the ESI Scheme in the organized sector and will also enable the ESI Corporation to participate in schemes such as Rashtriya Swasthya Bima Yojna (RSBY), that may be framed for the workers in the unorganized sector. The amendments are also aimed at improving service delivery to the existing members of ESI Scheme as well as bringing the provisions of the Act in tune with the changing circumstances (GOI, 2010)..

The Union Cabinet also gave its approval for introduction of a Bill in the coming Session of the Parliament for amendment of section 2(e) of the Payment of Gratuity Act. Under this act "Employee" means any person (other than an apprentice) who is employed for wages, whether the terms of such employment are expressed or implied, in any kind of work, manual or otherwise, in or in connection with the work of a factory, mine, oilfield, plantation, port, railway company, shop or other establishment, to which this Act applies, but does not include any such person who holds a post under the Central Government or a State Government and is governed by any other Act or by any rules providing for the payment of gratuity. This will result in coverage of teachers in the educational institutions under the Payment of Gratuity Act, 1972 (GOI, 2010).

One of the most beneficial acts for the employees was the amendment made to the Employees Compensation Act, 1923. The Workmen's Compensation Act 1923 was enacted to help workmen face the hardships resulting from accidents. These legal provisions apply equally to women workers also. An employer is liable to provide monetary compensation to a disabled workman, or to his dependents, in case of his death, if the disablement or death occurs "out of and in the course of employment." The Workmen's Compensation Act has been amended to make it gender neutral and it is now called "the Employees' Compensation Act, 1923. Besides this, the Compensation in case of death, disablement and funeral expense paid under the Act have also been enhanced. The Plantation Labour Act, 1951 has been amended to provide safety and occupational health care to plantation workers (labour.nic.in/content/).

The Maternity Benefit (Amendment) Bill, 2008 to provide for (i) enhancing Medical Bonus from Rs. 250/- to Rs. 1,000/- if no prenatal confinement and post-natal care is provided by the employer free of charge; and (ii) Granting powers to the Central Government to revise Medical Bonus before three years subject to a maximum of Rs. 20,000/- has been passed by the Parliament. The Bill has also received the assent of the President on 1st April, 2008 and has been published in the Gazette of India on 2nd April, 2008.

The Government has instead proposed a more moderate approach, tweaking the legislation to deal with some of the more common issues.

Changes are also expected in the Privacy Act 1993. Although formal details of the Act are not yet released, recommendations for change focus largely on clarification of the principle-based

approach of the current act. Key recommendations also include streamlining the privacy complaints system, and modifying some exceptions. (Ministry of Labour and Employment, Govt. of India)

An interim Pension Fund Regulatory and Development Authority (PFRDA) was set up in 2003. The New Pension System (NPS), which was implemented in January 2004, shifted the pension schemes from the defined benefit system to the defined contribution system. The PFRDA Bill, 2011, seeks to give statutory status to the interim PFRDA, define its powers and duties, and set the broad contours of the NPS. Pension Fund Regulatory and Development Authority Bill, 2011 seeks to give statutory powers to the interim authority set up in 2003. It also alters the name of the New Pension System to National Pension System (NPS). NPS is a 'defined contribution' scheme for all central government employees who joined after January 2004. It is implemented through a combination of retailers, pension fund managers, and a record keeper. This scheme is different from the earlier 'defined benefit' scheme. Under the NPS, every subscriber will have an individual pension account, which will be portable across job changes. The subscribers will choose fund managers and schemes to manage their pension wealth. They will also have the option of switching schemes and fund managers.

Also, observing the huge difference between the wages of regular and contract labour was leading to unrest the government also amended the Contract Labour Act, 1970.

The Factories Act 1948 is meant to offer safety to the workers from being exploited by the greedy business establishments and it also provides for the improvement of working conditions within the factory premises. Hence, a beneficial construction should be given and the provisions of the Act should be so construed/ interpreted so as to achieve its object, i.e., the welfare of the workers and their protection from exploitation and unhygienic working conditions in the factory premises. (Factories Act 1948)

The Payment of Bonus Act, 1948 was also amended in 2010. According to the act bonus shall be provided to employees covered under the act. Employee means any person employed on a salary or wage not exceeding ten thousand rupees in any industry. The Act therefore provides bonus to only those employees whose salaries do not exceed ten thousand rupees. The Principal Employer has to ensure whether the Bonus is paid to the Contract Employees or not. In the Wage Pattern itself, the Principal Employer has to make the break up which is

inclusive of Bonus. The Bonus Act may talk about the Infancy Period i.e., any organization's age is below 5 years that has been exempted to pay Bonus, but in the same act it is clearly mentioned that, if the Organization starts to getting Profit within 2 years, then it has to pay the Bonus to its employees from the Origin with Interest attribution, (Ministry of Labour and Employment, GOI, 2010)

The umbrella legislation relating to provident fund is [the Employees' Provident Funds & Miscellaneous Provisions Act, 1952 \(EPF & MP Act\)](#). The Act was enacted with the main objective of making some provisions for the future of industrial workers after their retirement and for their dependents in case of death. It provides insurance to workers and their dependents against risks of old age, retirement, discharge, retrenchment or death of the workers. It is [applicable](#) to every establishment, which is engaged in any one, or more of the industries specified in Schedule I of the Act or any activity notified by Central Government in the Official Gazette and employing 20 or more persons. (Provident Fund Act)

The government has also passed a Privacy Law. The Information and Technology (Reasonable Security Practices and Procedures and Sensitive Personal Data or Information) Rules, 2011 ('the Rules'), has introduced a privacy law regarding personal information. Personal data could consist of passwords, sexual orientation, mental health conditions, etc.

Important amendments have also been made to the Trade Union Act, 1926. Under section 22, the act with the proportion office bearers to be connected with the industry. Before the amendment the section provided that not less than one half of the office bearers of a trade union shall have to be persons actually engaged in the industry with the trade union is connected. A new sub section, which has been introduced after the amendment, stipulates that in other than unorganized sector unions, all office bearers except not more than one third or five whichever is less should be from the industry i.e. outsiders can be office bearers only up to one third of the total office bearers posts, not more than 7 can be outsiders. (Ministry of Labour and Employment, Govt. of India).

Despite many labour laws being passed to protect the interest of the employees and to maintain decorum between the relationship of the employer and the employee it does deter the violation of labour laws. The Maruti Udyog case is one of the prime examples of labour law violations. Among other cases the Common Wealth Games as well as the Bangalore Metro

Rail Corporation have been booked under violation of labour laws like lack of proper working conditions and irregular payment of wages. Likewise there can be many cases booked under the court of law for violating the Labor Laws. However, Keeping up to the Legislation will be a major advantage to the organizations, as well as employees will be satisfied and more committed to their own work. Keeping up to the legislations also gives a sense of security to the employees, which can be women safety, job security, fair wages, workplace safety, and many more. The employee engagement is not too far for any organization, if they keep up to the legislations.

For achieving these, updating of the amendments becomes an integral part and a necessary component. Training to the dedicated HR manager becomes very important for the same.

TRAINING ON AMENDMENTS

HR officers and managers need to understand the legal framework that supports the employment relationship. The responsible officers should be identified and sent to training of legal amendments on a continuous basis. The HR professionals should be able to identify key employment rights and responsibilities that have a direct impact on the workplace. The training also allows them to gain confidence in tackling the issues, negotiating, and presence of mind. The officers should also be trained on resolving everyday issues fairly and under the radar of law. They should also made to maintain proper documentation, and all the procedures to be well understood by both employers and employees. Ideally the training has to be provided to the employees also by the same HR officer, so that they also understand the legislations, its amendments, and know the boundaries of law. The communication of the amendments has to be transparent and complete. It has to be ethical.

OBSERVATIONS

The growth performance of the economy though not spectacular has been decent, by the growth in the standard of living. However, this has not lead to improvement in the working conditions of the employees. In fact the development of the working conditions has been quite low. Many problems arise due to the negligence on the part of the employers as well as employees.

“Ignorantia juris non excusat”, court does not accept ignorance of the law. An HR professional because of illiteracy and ignorance cannot state that they are not aware of the law. Labour laws

are the backbone of human resource management. Human resource management holds no validity without labour laws and sometimes violation of these laws could lead to severe legal problems.

Typically managers may be faced with dilemmas in situations like sexual harassment cases, violation of working conditions. It is difficult to establish ground rules for behaviour in such cases. Hence, the HR professionals usually find it cumbersome to keep up with the dealings of such cases. Inability to deal with these situations effectively can lead to disgruntled employees or resentful employees.

Sexual harassment cases are typically of delicate nature. Decision-making is hard due to the fragile nature of such cases. With the establishment of sexual harassment laws the Hr can take direct decisions of dismissal or punishment owing to a zero tolerance policy of sexual harassment in the workplace. If the professionals are not well informed of the policies in advance they may not conduct the investigation thoroughly and the result may be bias or even unfair and inadequate in some cases. If the Hr will consistently follow through with the policies it can take swift corrective action if the harassment does occur and these steps may prevent the risk of liability to a company, or at least reduce the risk of the damage award.

The Employee State Benefits Act emphasizes the need for better working conditions for the workers of a firm. If the hr professionals are not well informed of the necessary requirements to fulfill the guidelines it could lead to unhappy employees. Lack of an efficient work place will also affect the profitability of an employee. If the employee feels dissatisfied with the working conditions he/she may not be motivated to work whole-heartedly for the organizations. Thus, it is necessary for the hr to keep a track of the new developments to ensure employee satisfaction. This act also specifies the need for payments of monetary sum in the advent of any emergencies. Absence of payments could lead to lawsuits in the firm and accusations of embezzlement of funds.

Similarly, the workmen’s compensation act also provides for compensation in the advent of the death of the employee. The compensation is provided to the employee’s family. Non-payment of such funds could lead to embezzlement charges. It could also tarnish the firm’s reputation as being unsympathetic to the need of the employee and pursuing an inhuman nature.

The Payment of Gratuity Act also provides for the payment of gratuity to employees engaged in factories, mines etc. prompt payment of gratuity can help to motivate the employees. Gratuity will also boost the morale of the employee. It can be used as a tool of appreciation for the employees' good work. The hr must keep up date with such information, as they need to continuously motivate their employees. Monetary benefits are one of the most effective tools of motivation of the employees.

Acts like the Maternity Benefit Act or the Paternity Benefit Act help the firm to earn a fair share of goodwill. If the hr is well informed and lenient in the practice of these acts it will help the firm to build a social standing rather than just focus on their respective markets.

Every law was fabricated for a specific purpose. Labour laws were formed for the protection of the employees who are employed by an individual or firm. Every HR manager must be up to date with the laws because the core functions of an organization are linked with the labour laws of the respective countries. For example, The Industrial Disputes Act or the Minimum Wages Act forms the basis of recruiting employees and deciding their pay packages.

Maintaining proper relations between the employer and the employee is imperative to an organization. Having good labour relations can improve the productivity of the organization. Such a situation is only possible when the hr continually renews their knowledge about the laws and rights of the employees.

Arising of disputes is common in an organization. However, it is necessary to minimize these disputes. Many such disputes can be solved taking into account the Industrial Disputes Act, 1946. Lack of knowledge about the amendments may hinder effective handling of disputes and may even create disharmony in the organization.

Welfare, safety issues are very important to an organization and must be maintained in accordance to the Factories Act 1948.

Every human resource manager should possess a thorough knowledge of the countries labour laws. Many of the human resource functions are based on labour laws and should be implemented in accordance with the labour laws. Critical disputes like issues involving women, employees' rules and regulations in mining, child labour and compensation in case of accidents must be conducted accordingly to the labour laws strictly. Failure to do so can lead

to resentful employees. These resentful employees by word of mouth can also create a negative image of the firm in the market. The firm could be viewed as an unconcerned employer.

In the advent of the decline of the Industrial Relations the job of the HR professionals has increased manifold. The role of Personnel Manager is converted in to HR Manager, and the roles are upgraded over a period of time right from 1920's to 2010. Post Industrial revolution, Independence has brought a lot of reforms in the legislations and welfare of the people. Post LPG, the acts are being continuously amended; however, many employers have not update with latest legislations. Once the employees know the amendment of acts from an outsider, the unrest will cause and the trust on employer will die slowly. The new approach of treating employees as assets to the organization has declined a number of union memberships which has fallen from 12 million to around 7 million today. The range of issues over which bargaining took place decreased massively. The Workplace Employment Relations Survey (WERS) showed that union officials spent most of their time not on negotiating pay and conditions but in supporting grievances on behalf of individual members. Even where collective bargaining continued, its impact on the exercise of management discretion was greatly diminished. (cipd.co.uk). The shift in the coverage and content of collective bargaining has been reflected in a dramatic reduction in industrial action since 1980. The number of working days lost per 1,000 union members decreased from an annual average of 1,163 in the 1970s to 76 in the 1990s. They remain low and are below the levels in many other developed countries. Thus, Industrial Relations remain a lost tool to an organization. Most of the functions have been taken over by the HR function.

Thus, the growing need for the HR professional to be up to date with the labour laws can only be justified. Lack of knowledge of union laws can lead the company to severe losses. It can lead to plant shutdowns, strikes and all other issues that directly affect the productivity of a firm. In spite of having such a high potential in manufacturing sector whether in SME's, or heavy industries, the legislations and ethics keep the organizations maintain healthy environment. The physical visit to many organizations for this research purpose by the authors, revealed some facts explained further.

The products manufactured by most of the SME's sector are unique and mainly B2B products, and hardly anyone has competitor. Every organization has work orders from huge

multinational companies or government. Having the projects in hand they are unable to sustain and closing the units just because they have no much idea on legal aspects, and its amendments. Many proprietors have mentioned that due to financial status, they cannot hire legal consultants, and as such they have a partial knowledge on the legal matters. If proprietors are trained, or the responsible HR officer or supervisor is trained, organizations will know its boundaries, and also employees will understand which will turn into a healthy and successful organization.

CONCLUSION

In spite a booming economy companies have always dealt with HR issues that never seem to end. For many organizations, attrition rates are high which is a direct indicator for organizational health. Employers judge attrition as the inability of the HR to match up with the industry standards as well as the labour laws.

HR issues must be solved in time and never be delayed. Preferable HR should be proactive than a reactive. This can be possible only if there is trained HR officer, open communication, transparency in policies. If they are not resolved in time, employee may also approach labour courts, which is a very time consuming procedure. Labour courts also involve unnecessary use of the organizational resources that could have been put to better use. Timely decision making and being ethical and under the radar of law is the key to organization success. When time matters in leads to the cost of the organization, with proper knowledge of labour laws by the HR professionals can help resolve conflicts and address employee issues promptly accordingly to the laws and save time.

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